

**HIGH-SENSITIVITY MICROSTRIP SPLIT RING RESONATOR (SRR) SENSOR
FOR ACCURATE SOIL MOISTURE CONTENT CHARACTERIZATION**

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Abstract: This study presents the design, simulation, and evaluation of a microstrip-based Split Ring Resonator (SRR) sensor for precise characterization of soil moisture content through dielectric property measurement. Three SRR geometries—square, circular, and hexagonal—were developed and optimized to resonate at 1.3 GHz using microstrip technology with a Rogers 6010LM substrate. The sensor operates by detecting shifts in resonant frequency caused by variations in the soil's dielectric constant as moisture content changes. Electromagnetic simulations using CST Microwave Studio were performed to analyze transmission parameter, followed by soil-loading tests with sandy soil samples placed as a superstrate over the sensor. Results demonstrate a measurable frequency shift correlating linearly with moisture content and relative permittivity changes. Among the configurations, the circular SRR exhibited the highest sensitivity ($\sim 3.09\%$), while the square SRR offered the most compact design and good linearity ($R^2 \approx 0.9902$). The sensor shows promise for cost-effective, non-invasive soil moisture monitoring applicable in agriculture and environmental management.

Keywords : Microstrip Split Ring Resonator, Soil Moisture Sensor, Dielectric Characterization, Resonant Frequency Shift, Sensitivity